
TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS OF TEACHER EDUCATORS AS RELATED TO GENDER AND PROFESSIONAL COMMITMENT

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ABSTRACT

The present study was carried out to investigate the teaching effectiveness of teacher educators in relation to gender and professional commitment. Survey technique under Descriptive research method was used in this study. A representative sample of 269 teacher educators from 27 B.Ed. colleges of Himachal Pradesh was collected by employing Incidental sampling technique. Data were collected with the help of Teaching Effectiveness Scale by Dr. Umme Kulsum and Professional Commitment Scale by Dr. Ravinder Kaur, Dr. Sarbjit Ranu and Mrs. Sarvjeet Kaur Barar. Descriptive statistics and Statistical Technique of Analysis of variance ANOVA (Two-Way) were used to analyze the data. The results of the study indicated that male and female teacher educators do not differ significantly with respect to their teaching effectiveness. There exists no significant difference in the teaching effectiveness of teacher educators with respect to different level of work motivation. Gender and work motivation interact significantly with respect to their teaching experience. At the end of the paper, implications of the study have been discussed.

Keywords: Teaching Effectiveness, Gender, Work Motivation.

INTRODUCTION

Effectiveness of the teachers is as par excellence attribute of the teaching excellence. In this modern era, the effectiveness of teachers becomes vital to face the emerging challenges of globalization and mushrooming of the educational institutions. Teacher's effectiveness can be defined as an "act of faith". The most accepted criteria for measuring good teaching is the amount of student learning that occurs. A teacher's effectiveness is about student's learning. An effective teacher not only knows the subject matter he intends to learn to his students, but also knows the misconceptions his students bring to the classrooms, which are going to interfere with the learning of subject matter. The expectation on teachers to respond to current reform initiatives influences their professional lives in a number of ways. Professional commitment is "the degree to which a person's work performance affects his self-esteem". For a person who is professionally committed work is a vital part of life for him. This means that both the work itself and the co-workers are very meaningful to the employee, in additions to the importance she/he attaches to organization as a whole. Teachers' successful participation in decision-making could be explained by the feeling of ownership that comes from initiating ideas rather than responding to others' proposal. A professionally committed teacher gives equal importance and chance to all students at the right time to ensure optimum achievement. A committed teacher acts as an active school-classroom manager, leader and organizer of the group activities, builder of pupil's character and is often expected to undertake and promote learner activities. It is the urge of a teacher to update, strengthen and sharpen his professional competencies and to develop understanding and insight in different aspects of a profession. **Bala and Bashir (2016)** revealed that there existed no significant relationship between teaching effectiveness and work motivation. This proved that work

motivation had no role to play in deciding the teaching effectiveness of teachers. Further, the value of correlation was very negligible in nature which again inferred that teaching effectiveness and correlation were not significantly interrelated to each other. **Manju (2017)** found that female teachers have high level of teaching effectiveness when comparing to their male counterparts. The study also revealed that no significant difference was found between secondary school teachers belonging to government, private aided and private unaided secondary school teachers with respect to their teaching effectiveness. **Halder and Roy (2018)** revealed that there was a positive and statistically significant correlation between teacher adjustment and teacher effectiveness. The correlation between teacher adjustment and teacher effectiveness as well as teacher adjustment and all five aspects of teacher effectiveness (personal aspect, professional aspect; intellectual aspect; strategies aspect; and social aspect) were not statistically significant for the male teachers. Hence, it may be stated that there is no statistically significant correlation between teacher adjustment and teacher effectiveness for male teachers. It was also found that there were positive and statistically significant correlations between teacher adjustment and teacher effectiveness of the urban teachers but no significant relation between these two variables for the rural teachers was found. **Rasool and Mattoo (2019)** revealed that there was significant influence of gender on teacher effectiveness and type of school had significant influence on teacher effectiveness. Furthermore, it was also revealed that gender and type of school had significant influence on teacher effectiveness of secondary school teachers. **Singh and Attri (2020)** revealed that teacher effectiveness of male secondary school teachers do not differ significantly from their counterpart female secondary school teachers. Teacher effectiveness of male and female secondary school teachers was equal. Further, findings showed that teacher effectiveness of rural and urban secondary school teachers was not equal. It means that urban secondary school teachers have better teacher effectiveness as compared to rural secondary school teachers. **Raju and Vardhini (2021)** found the significant difference between the secondary school teachers working in rural and urban areas with respect to teacher effectiveness. Further, it was also showed that there was a significant difference between married and unmarried secondary school teachers with respect to teacher effectiveness. There was a no significant difference between the mean scores of teacher effectiveness among secondary school teachers based on type of school. In addition to this, the findings of the study also found that there was a significant difference between teaching experiences of secondary school teachers with respect to teacher effectiveness.

It has been observed on the basis of the thorough review of the literature that very few studies are on teaching effectiveness of teacher educators. Hence, it was decided to see the impact of gender and professional commitment on teaching effectiveness of teacher educators.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the gender-wise difference among teacher educators with respect to their teaching effectiveness.
2. To study the difference in teaching effectiveness of teacher educators with respect to their level of professional commitment.
3. To study the interactional effect of gender and professional commitment on teaching effectiveness of teacher educators.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

1. There will be no significant gender-wise difference among teacher educators with respect to their teaching effectiveness.

2. There will be no significant difference in teaching effectiveness of teacher educators with respect to their level of professional commitment.
3. There will be no significant interactional effect of gender and professional commitment on teaching effectiveness of teacher educators.

METHODOLOGY

Survey technique under descriptive research was used to fulfill the objectives of the study.

SAMPLING

A representative sample of 269 teacher educators was selected from 27 B.Ed. colleges of Bilaspur, Kangra, Mandi, Kullu and Shimla districts of Himachal Pradesh by applying incidental sampling technique in the present study.

RESEARCH TOOLS USED

In the present study, following research tools were used to collect the data:

1. Teacher Effectiveness scale by Umme Kulsum (2011).
2. Professional Commitment Scale by Dr. Ravinder Kaur, Dr. Sarbjit Ranu and Mrs. Sarvjeet Kaur Barar (2011).

ANALYSIS OF DATA

Descriptive statistics and analysis of variance (Two-Way ANOVA) were used to analyze the data. Detail description of the analysis is given below:

In order to study the main effects of gender and professional commitment on teaching effectiveness of teacher educators along with their interactional effect, analysis of variance (2 x 3 factor design) involving two level of gender i.e. male and female and three level of professional commitment i.e. high, moderate and low was applied on mean scores of teaching effectiveness. The sampled teacher educators were classified by employing the procedure of $M \pm 1SD$. The mean teaching effectiveness scores of teacher educators with respect to gender and level of professional commitment are given in table 1.

TABLE 1

MEANS AND STANDARD DEVIATIONS OF TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS SCORES OF TEACHER EDUCATORS WITH RESPECT TO GENDER AND PROFESSIONAL COMMITMENT

Sr. No.	Levels of Professional Commitment Gender		Mean Teaching Effectiveness Scores			
			High Level	Moderate Level	Low Level	Total
1	Male (63)	Mean	504.31	510.00	497.43	501.29
		S.D.	23.932	51.783	73.758	49.573
		N	13	43	7	63
2	Female (206)	Mean	510.16	487.38	498.84	493.03
		S.D.	13.669	73.975	60.941	66.147
		N	32	136	38	206
3	Total (269)	Mean	508.47	490.65	498.62	494.97
		S.D.	17.176	69.405	62.169	62.671
		N	45	179	45	269

From mean teaching effectiveness scores of male and female teacher educators with respect to their level of professional commitment, F- ratio were calculated. The summary of results of analysis of variance is given in Table 2 as follows:

TABLE 2

SUMMARY OF ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE FOR TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS OF TEACHER EDUCATORS WITH RESPECT TO GENDER AND PROFESSIONAL COMMITMENT

Sr. No.	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square (Variance)	F-Ratio
1.	Gender(A)	131.166	1	131.166	0.033 ^{NS}
2.	Professional Commitment (B)	4925.208	2	2462.604	0.626 ^{NS}
3.	Gender× Professional Commitment (A×B)	3327.744	2	1663.872	0.423 ^{NS}
4.	ErrorVariance	1034101.873	263	3931.946	
5.	Total	1052620.699	268		

NS-NOT SIGNIFICANT

Main Effects

(a) Gender (A)

It may be seen from the table 2 that the computed F-Ratio showing the main effect of gender on teaching effectiveness of teacher educators, for degree of freedom 1 and 263, came out to be 0.033, which is less than the F-table value(3.87) at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, Hypothesis no. 1 that, “There will be no significant gender-wise difference among teacher educators with respect to their teaching effectiveness,” was retained. Thus, it is concluded that male and female teacher educators do not differ significantly in their teaching effectiveness and possessed almost similar level of teaching effectiveness. However, on the basis of mean scores, male teacher educators possessed high teaching effectiveness (501.29) as compared to female teacher educators (493.03). The mean teaching effectiveness scores of male and female teacher educators can also be shown from Figure 1 as follows:

FIGURE 1

MEAN TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS SCORES OF TEACHER EDUCATORS WITH RESPECT TO THEIR GENDER

(b) Professional commitment (B)

The computed value of F-Ratio for the main effect of professional commitment on teaching effectiveness of teacher educators, for degree of freedom 2 and 263, came out to be 0.626, which is less than the table value (3.03) at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, Hypothesis no. 2 that, “There will be no significant difference in teaching effectiveness of teacher educators with respect to their level of professional commitment,” was retained. So, this is indicative of the fact that there is no significant difference in the teaching effectiveness of teacher educators with regard to different level of professional commitment.

Further it may be seen from table that mean value of teaching effectiveness scores obtained by high, moderate and low professionally committed teachers found to be 508.47, 490.65 and 498.62 respectively. However, it was inferred from the mean values that teacher educators with high professional commitment (508.47) possessed more teaching effectiveness as compared to teacher educators having moderate professional commitment (490.65) and low professional commitment (498.62). The mean teaching effectiveness scores of teacher educators with respect to levels of professional commitment is given in Figure 2 as follows:

FIGURE 2

MEAN TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS SCORES OF TEACHER EDUCATORS WITH RESPECT TO LEVELS OF PROFESSIONAL COMMITMENT

Interactional Effect (A X B)

The obtained value of ‘F’- for interactional effect of gender and professional commitment on teaching effectiveness of teacher educators, for degree of freedom 2 and 263, came out to be 0.423, which is not significant even at 0.05 level of significance. In the light of this, Hypothesis no 3 that,” There will be no significant interactional effect of gender and professional commitment on teaching effectiveness of teacher educators,” was retained.

Form above analysis, it can be revealed that gender and professional commitment (in combination with each other) do not have significant interactional effect on teaching effectiveness of teacher educators.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The computed F-Ratio showing the main effect of gender on teaching effectiveness of teacher educators, for degree of freedom 1 and 263, came out to be 0.033, which is less than the F-table value(3.87) at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, it is concluded

that male and female teacher educators do not differ significantly in their teaching effectiveness and possessed almost similar level of teaching effectiveness. However, on the basis of mean scores, it was inferred that male teacher educators possessed high teaching effectiveness (501.29) as compared to female teacher educators (493.03).

2. The computed value of F-Ratio for the main effect of professional commitment on teaching effectiveness of teacher educators, for degree of freedom 2 and 263, came out to be 0.626, which is less than the table value (3.03) at 0.05 level of significance. So, this is indicative of the fact that there is no significant difference in the teaching effectiveness of teacher educators with regard to different level of professional commitment. Further it may be seen from table that mean value of teaching effectiveness scores obtained by high, moderate and low professionally committed teachers found to be 508.47, 490.65 and 498.62 respectively. However, it was inferred from the mean values that teacher educators with high professional commitment (508.47) possessed more teaching effectiveness as compared to teacher educators having moderate professional commitment (490.65) and low professional commitment (498.62).
3. The obtained value of 'F'- for interactional effect of gender and professional commitment on teaching effectiveness of teacher educators, for degree of freedom 2 and 263, came out to be 0.423, which is not significant even at 0.05 level of significance. In the light of this, it can be revealed that gender and professional commitment (in combination with each other) do not have significant interactional effect on teaching effectiveness of teacher educators.

IMPLICATIONS

The present investigation was conducted to study the teaching effectiveness of teacher educators with respect to gender and professional commitment. After drawing out the results from the study, it was found that there was no significant difference in teaching effectiveness of male and female teacher educators. However, on the basis of mean scores, it was concluded that male teacher educators have reflected somewhat higher teaching effectiveness as compared to female teacher educators. It is therefore essential that some efforts should be made by educationist, policy planners and authorities to increase the teaching effectiveness of female teacher educators. It was also found that teacher educators with high professional commitment possessed higher teaching effectiveness as compared to teacher educators having moderate and low level of professional commitment. If teachers effectively play their role, they will be in a position to fulfill the educational objective as well as national goals. Therefore, it can be said that if a teacher is aware of the new techniques, classroom management, instructional strategies and professional values, will give his/her best efforts to the profession and moreover, will be more committed to his/her profession.

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